

TABLE 2

Inhibitor	Ratio of copper/zinc in 0.2M (Potassium-persulphate (Values in the bracket represent inhibitor concentration in ml/l or percentage)				
	5 min.	15 min.	30 min.	60 min.	90 min.
Nil	2.65	4.04	2.15	2.58	2.25
Paraldehyde	4.98	3.79	4.69	—	3.49
	(2.17 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	—	(17.40 ml/l)
Salicylaldehyde	0.7	2.3	3.1	1.54	2.57
	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)	(8.70 ml/l)

In the presence of paraldehyde, the potential values are more negative throughout than those in its absence. The potential values in the presence of 26.10 ml/l paraldehyde are more negative than those in the presence of 8.70 ml/l paraldehyde which is in good agreement with the higher efficiency with increased concentration of the inhibitor.

In the presence of 26.10 ml/l paraldehyde, there is considerable cathode polarization, the anode is also polarized to a certain extent. Thus, paraldehyde is a mixed type of inhibitor with the predominance of cathodic action.

Furfuraldehyde: In general, the efficiency of furfuraldehyde decreases with the passage of time. At 17.40 ml/l concentration, the excellent inhibitive action of furfuraldehyde is felt immediately.

In the presence of 34.80 ml/l furfuraldehyde, the potential values are more negative than those in its absence indicating its action on local cathodes. In the presence of 17.40 ml/l furfuraldehyde, the potential values are more negative upto fifteen minutes, thereafter the values are practically identical in the presence and absence of the inhibitor.

Furfuraldehyde induces strong cathode polarization. However, the effect of the inhibitor on the local anodes is not quite perceptible from the polarization measurements.

Salicylaldehyde: Salicylaldehyde is an excellent inhibitor which affords more than 98% protection to 70/30 brass even at as low a concentration as 0.43 ml/l. The optimum concentration of salicylaldehyde is 4.35 ml/l, the further increase in the inhibitor concentration induces a slight decrease in its efficiency. The efficiency of salicylaldehyde is nearly constant from fifteen to 90 min.

In the presence of 2.17 ml/l salicylaldehyde, the potential values are throughout more negative indicating its action on local cathodes. In the presence of 8.70 ml/l salicylaldehyde, the potential values are less negative than those in the presence of 2.17 ml/l salicylaldehyde which is in good agreement with the decreased efficiency of salicylaldehyde beyond, 2.17 ml/l concentration.

Salicylaldehyde induces significant cathode polarization. The anode is also polarized in the presence of salicylaldehyde. The higher inhibition action of 2.17

ml/l salicylaldehyde is evident from the increased cathode and anode polarization in its presence, as compared with the values obtained in the presence of 8.70 ml/l salicylaldehyde.

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Nitrate and Nitrite Derivatives of Diarylthallium(III) Cation

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SOME diorganothallium (III) nitrates (organo= CH_3 , C_6F_5 , and C_6H_5) have been synthesised either by the interaction of diorganothallium (III) iodide and silver nitrate^{1,2} or by heating organothallium oxide with concentrated nitric acid in glacial acetic acid³. The infrared spectra of the compounds indicate weak nitrate co-ordination resulting in a bridging structure, but the high conductance in methanol is consistent with the presence of linear R_2TI^+ ions. Little is known about the corresponding organothallium (III) nitrites. In continuation to our studies on diarylthallium (III) derivative⁴⁻⁷ we now report the synthesis and characterisation of some diarylthallium (III) nitrates and nitrites (aryl = phenyl, o-tolyl, m-tolyl or p-tolyl).

Experimental

Diarylthallium (III) chlorides were synthesised by the reported method⁸. Other reagents of analytical grade were obtained from British Drug Houses. Dimethyl formamide was freshly distilled under reduced pressure before use in conductometric measurements.

In a typical preparation 1 m mole of diarylthallium (III) chloride in 50 ml pyridine-water mixture was treated with a concentrated aqueous solution of excess of sodium nitrate or nitrite (5 m mole) and the mixture stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The precipitated diarylthallium (III) derivative was filtered, washed with water, ethanol, finally with diethyl ether and dried. The melting points, the analytical data of the compounds and their infrared active anionic absorptions are presented in Table 1.

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TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR R₂TIX

R	X	m.p. °C	Analytical data, found (calcd) % element				IR absorption bands				
			TI	C	H	N	ν_3	ν_1	ν_2	ν_4	Combina- tion band
phenyl	NO ₃	>320	48.7 (48.6)	34.6 (34.3)	2.5 (2.4)	3.2 (3.3)	1380 vs	1042 m	808 w	b	1750 w
<i>o</i> -tolyl	„	308-10d	46.0 (45.5)	37.9 (37.5)	2.9 (3.1)	3.2 (3.1)	1380 vs	1038 s	812 w	705 w	1745 w
<i>m</i> -tolyl ^a	„	318 d	45.9	37.3	3.2	3.3	1380 vs	1040 w	805 w	710 m	1750 w
<i>p</i> -tolyl ^a	„	>320	46.0	38.0	3.3	3.2	1370 vs	1038 m	815 w	715 m	1755 w
phenyl	NO ₂	>320	50.5 (50.5)	36.0 (35.6)	2.5 (2.3)	3.5 (3.5)	1208 vs	1325 sh	833 m	—	2490 w
<i>o</i> -tolyl	„	297-99d	47.5 (47.2)	39.5 (38.8)	2.9 (3.2)	3.3 (3.2)	1210 s	1325 vs	840 w	—	—
<i>m</i> -tolyl ^a	„	262 d	47.6	38.9	3.4	3.4	1200 vs	1335 vs	830 m	—	2520 w
<i>p</i> -tolyl ^a	„	292 d	47.4	39.1	3.3	3.3	1210 vs	1335 s	835 m	—	2480 w

a=calculated data for m and p tolyl derivatives are the same as for o-tolyl

b=masked by C-H out of plane deformation

d=decomposes

s=strong, m=medium, sh=shoulder, v=very, w=weak

The compounds are white solids, insoluble in common organic solvents such as benzene, chloroform, diethyl ether etc., but dissolve appreciably in pyridine, dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulphoxide. They decompose around 300° before melting. Molar conductance of 10⁻³M solution in dimethyl formamide at 35° is found to be in the range 58.2 - 80.6 ohm⁻¹ cm² moles⁻¹, indicating 1 : 1 electrolytic character of the compounds.

The infrared spectra of the compounds in nujol were recorded in the region 4000 - 400 cm⁻¹ using Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer model 337. The absorptions associated with the aromatic group are observed at position reported by us in one of our earlier publications⁷, are not listed here. The absorptions associated with various modes of vibration of the nitrate and nitrite groups are summarised in the last column of the Table.

In the spectra of diarylthallium (III) nitrates, four absorptions located at 1375 ± 5, 1040 ± 2, 810 ± 5, and 710 ± 5 cm⁻¹ are assigned to asym stretching ν_3 , sym stretching ν_1 , bending ν_2 and planar rocking ν_4 modes of vibration of the nitrate group respectively. The values are in the range reported for ionic nitrates⁸, and thus strongly support our conductance data suggesting the compounds to be 1 : 1 electrolytes. An absorption of weak intensity occurring in the spectra of all diarylthallium (III) nitrates at 1750 ± 5 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to a combination band denoted by $\nu_1 + \nu_4$.

In the spectra of the four newly synthesised diarylthallium(III) nitrites three anionic absorptions namely ν_1 and ν_3 associated with the stretching modes of the NO₂ group and ν_2 , the bending mode, appear at 1330 ± 5, 1205 ± 5 and 835 ± 5 cm⁻¹ respectively. The results suggest ionic character of the nitrites in view of the reported data of Sidman⁹ on sodium nitrite and support our high conductance values in dimethylformamide solution. Besides the three fundamental modes of absorption, a weak combination or overtone at 2500 ± 20 cm⁻¹ is also observed which may be either $\nu_1 + \nu_3$ or $2\nu_3$.

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Preparation and Characterisation of Double Acetates of Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II)

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ANHYDROUS acetates of nickel (II) and cobalt (II) are insoluble in acetic anhydride but they readily form clear solutions when alkali metal and thallos and ammonium acetates are added to their solutions. Nothing separates out when these solutions are either chilled or some inert solvent is added. However yellow (nickel) and violet (cobalt) compounds separate out when ether is added to these solutions.